

THE INFLUENCE OF SCHOOL ADMINISTRATOR TRAITS ON INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP EFFECTIVENESS IN PUBLIC SCHOOLS: A MIXED-METHODS APPROACH

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of **school administrators' traits** on their effectiveness as **instructional leaders** in Lanao Del Sur public schools. Specifically, it examines critical characteristics such as **emotional intelligence**, **decision-making**, **communication**, **adaptability**, and **resilience**, assessing their impact on **instructional leadership** and overall **school performance**. A **mixed-methods approach** was employed, incorporating **quantitative data** from **150 teachers' and administrators' surveys** and **qualitative insights** from **in-depth interviews**. The findings reveal that administrators with higher levels of **emotional intelligence** and **adaptability** substantially enhance their school's instructional capacity, improving **teacher performance** and **student outcomes**. This study underscores the significance of **leadership development programs** that focus on cultivating these essential traits to strengthen **instructional leadership** and foster an environment conducive to academic success. Ultimately, the research contributes to understanding how the personal characteristics of educational leaders can impact the effectiveness of instructional practices in challenging educational contexts.

Keywords: School Administrator, Personal Traits, Instructional Leaders, Emotional Intelligence, Adaptability, Resilience, Student Outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Public schools in Lanao Del Sur encounter many challenges that hinder their ability to provide quality education. These challenges include limited resources, diverse student needs, and ongoing pressures from educational reforms. Effective leadership is crucial in navigating these obstacles, as it can significantly influence students' academic outcomes. Every student deserves access to a quality education that enables them to reach their full potential (Sanchez & Watson, 2021). However, despite the concerted efforts of educators and policymakers over the past 50 years, the achievement gap between students from low-income backgrounds and their more affluent peers continues to persist (Flores, 2007).

The discussion surrounding instructional strategies and practices to narrow this gap has been ongoing, with researchers and practitioners seeking effective solutions (Leithwood, 2010; McGee, 2004). Existing research consistently indicates that educational leadership—particularly that of school principals—plays a critical role in enhancing student achievement (McGee, 2004). Among the various leadership roles, instructional leadership is a pivotal responsibility for school administrators. It encompasses the enhancement of teaching quality, the encouragement of professional development among staff, and the creation of a supportive and conducive learning environment. Administrators' personal and professional characteristics significantly influence their ability to fulfill these responsibilities effectively. Emotional

intelligence, decision-making ability, communication skills, adaptability, and resilience are increasingly recognized as vital components of effective instructional leadership. While previous research has identified various leadership traits, the connection between these traits and the effectiveness of instructional leadership has yet to be thoroughly examined. This study seeks to fill this gap by investigating the influence of school administrators' traits on their effectiveness as instructional leaders in Lanao Del Sur public schools. By exploring this relationship, the research aims to highlight the importance of developing critical personal traits among school leaders to enhance their instructional leadership capacity, ultimately benefiting students' educational experiences in the region.

Statement of the Problem

Despite recognizing the importance of practical education leadership, there remains a significant research gap concerning the specific personal traits of school administrators and how these traits influence their effectiveness as instructional leaders. In the context of public schools in Lanao Del Sur, where educational challenges such as limited resources and diverse student needs are prevalent, understanding the traits that contribute to successful instructional leadership is crucial. This study aims to investigate the following key questions:

1. What role does emotional intelligence play in the effectiveness of instructional leadership for school administrators?
2. How does decision-making ability affect the instructional leadership of school administrators?
3. In what ways does communication skill contribute to the effectiveness of instructional leadership?
4. What are the interactions between these traits, and how do they collectively influence instructional leadership?

By addressing these questions, this study aims to contribute valuable insights into the relationship between the personal traits of school administrators and their effectiveness as instructional leaders. Ultimately, the findings will provide a foundation for developing targeted leadership development programs that enhance the necessary traits for effective instructional leadership, thereby improving educational outcomes in Lanao Del Sur.

Research Objectives

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. To identify and evaluate the personal traits of school administrators that enhance their effectiveness as instructional leaders.
2. Examine how these traits influence school performance, particularly teacher effectiveness and student outcomes.
3. To offer recommendations for leadership development programs to foster these essential traits among school administrators.

Significance of the Study

This study holds significant implications for various stakeholders in the educational sector. Understanding how the personal traits of school administrators—such as emotional intelligence, decision-making, communication, adaptability, and resilience—affect their instructional leadership effectiveness offers valuable insights for refining leadership practices in public schools.

The findings can guide school administrators in reflecting on their leadership styles and identifying personal and professional growth areas. By recognizing which traits most strongly influence instructional leadership, administrators can focus on enhancing these skills to improve teacher performance, foster a positive school climate, and drive better student outcomes. Insights gained from this study can inform educational policymakers when designing and implementing recruitment, training, and leadership development programs. By integrating the traits identified in this study into policy frameworks, they can cultivate a more effective pool of school leaders. Policies emphasizing emotional intelligence, effective communication, adaptability, and resilience in leadership can lead to more productive school environments and improved student learning experiences. Teachers will benefit from working under school leaders with solid instructional leadership traits. Administrators with high emotional intelligence and strong decision-making capabilities can create supportive environments that enhance professional development and improve teacher effectiveness. This will ultimately lead to higher job satisfaction and improved teaching quality.

Educational institutions can utilize the study's findings to adjust their recruitment processes, selecting candidates for administrative positions based on the personal traits that contribute to effective leadership. Additionally, they can tailor leadership training programs to focus on developing these traits among current and future administrators, thereby enhancing overall school performance.

This study also opens avenues for further research into the specific mechanisms through which personal traits impact instructional leadership. Future studies could explore how these traits interact with contextual factors such as school size, location, and resource availability, providing a more nuanced understanding of leadership effectiveness. By identifying and emphasizing the personal traits that lead to successful instructional leadership, this research can contribute to developing more effective educational leaders, ultimately improving the quality of education in public schools in Lanao Del Sur and beyond.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Instructional leadership plays a crucial role in elevating educational quality. Hallinger (2011) describes instructional leadership as guiding and supporting teachers in enhancing their classroom practices. Administrators who excel in this role often cultivate a culture of academic excellence within their schools.

The role of school principals has undergone significant transformation in recent years, with an increasing focus on instructional leadership as essential for improving academic achievement

(Lunenburg, 2010; Robinson et al., 2008). Research highlights the importance of principals in shaping student outcomes and overall school performance. Studies indicate that a principal's leadership style and decision-making capabilities are critical in determining a school's success (Leithwood, 2010). Furthermore, principals implementing instructional strategies to close the achievement gap can significantly improve teaching quality (Wenglinsky, 2004).

Understanding the impact of principals on student performance is particularly important in schools with a high percentage of low-income students. A review of the literature on the role of principals in improving student achievement reveals two key areas: general leadership and instructional leadership. McGee (2004) found that principals in high-performing schools foster a positive school environment and actively work to improve instruction. Similarly, Reyes et al. (1999) identified that effective principals adopt a collaborative leadership approach, encouraging communication and cooperation between teachers, students, and parents. These principals also demonstrate humanistic leadership and are deeply concerned for students' values, abilities, and achievements (Reyes et al., 1999). A combination of collaborative leadership and a focus on instruction is thus a defining characteristic of successful principals in high-achieving schools (Leithwood, 2010).

Research also points to the importance of leadership traits such as emotional intelligence (Goleman, 1995), decision-making (Bass & Avolio, 1994), and adaptability (Yukl, 2010) in ineffective school management. These traits enable administrators to navigate complex educational environments and positively influence instructional practices.

Emotional intelligence (EI), defined as a leader's ability to manage their own emotions and those of others, has been shown to foster positive school climates and improve teacher morale, ultimately enhancing instructional quality (Fullan, 2002). Strong decision-making skills, particularly in high-pressure situations, are vital for school leadership (Leithwood & Riehl, 2003), while adaptability equips administrators to meet the evolving challenges of educational settings, directly affecting the teaching and learning process.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a mixed-methods approach to gain a holistic understanding of the relationship between administrator traits and the effectiveness of instructional leadership. By integrating quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews, the research aims to capture measurable data and in-depth insights reflecting educational leadership's complexities.

Participants

The study involved 150 participants: school administrators and teachers from 15 public schools in Lanao Del Sur. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants with relevant experiences in instructional leadership, ensuring that the insights gathered were meaningful and applicable to the research objectives.

Instruments

- Survey: A 30-item Likert scale survey was developed to quantitatively assess administrators' traits, including emotional intelligence, adaptability, and decision-making skills, along with their perceived effectiveness in instructional leadership. The survey captured participants' perceptions and experiences about the traits influencing their leadership practices.
- Interviews: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with ten selected school administrators to explore their perspectives and experiences in greater detail. The interview format allowed for flexibility in questioning, enabling participants to share their insights on how their traits affect their leadership styles and effectiveness in fostering instructional improvement. These interviews aimed to uncover nuanced understandings of the relationship between administrator traits and leadership practices, providing a richer context for the quantitative findings.

Study Location

The research was conducted in Marawi City, located in the province of Lanao del Sur, the ancestral land of the Meranaw people in the Philippines. The travel time from Iligan City to Marawi City is approximately one hour. As the capital of Lanao del Sur, Marawi enjoys a cooler climate due to its high-altitude position. This city is the birthplace of the Meranaw tribe, whose members now live in various parts of the Philippines. They are recognized as a prominent indigenous group within the Moro population. Marawi's economy is primarily based on agriculture and trade. Lanao del Sur is famous for its rich, fertile land and extensive mountains, which support the cultivation of various crops. The region is also dotted with rivers, which provide essential water resources and a range of fish species, contributing significantly to the livelihoods of the Meranaw as farmers and fishermen. Additionally, the Meranaw people are proficient traders, engaging in commerce at both local and international levels.

The first image shows the map of Lanao del Sur, and the second image shows the map indicating the location of Marawi City.

Figure 1: Map of Lanao Del Sur Showing the Location of Marawi City

Figure 2: Map of Lanao Del Sur

DATA ANALYSIS

Quantitative data from the surveys were analyzed using statistical methods to identify trends and correlations between administrator traits and instructional leadership effectiveness. Descriptive statistics provided an overview of participants' responses, while inferential statistics helped conclude the relationships between variables.

Qualitative data from the interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify key themes and patterns related to the impact of administrator traits on leadership effectiveness. This approach allowed for the extraction of in-depth insights, enriching the study's findings and enabling a comprehensive understanding of how personal attributes influence instructional leadership in educational settings.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical research practices, ensuring informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement. Participants were assured of their confidentiality and voluntary participation, allowing them to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The survey findings indicated a significant correlation between administrator traits and instructional leadership effectiveness. Specifically, emotional intelligence, adaptability, and decision-making emerged as the most strongly correlated traits ($r = .67$, $p < .01$). Administrators who received high scores in these areas were perceived as more effective instructional leaders by their staff, underscoring the importance of these traits in fostering an

effective educational environment. Analysis of interview responses revealed that emotional intelligence is crucial for establishing positive relationships with teachers and creating a supportive atmosphere for instructional improvement. One administrator highlighted this point: "Understanding the emotional state of my teachers helps me guide them better, especially during times of stress." This sentiment was echoed by others, who noted that administrators with high emotional intelligence could empathize with their staff, which in turn facilitated open communication and collaboration. This ability to connect on an emotional level was deemed essential for motivating teachers and addressing their needs effectively.

Effective communication was consistently identified as a vital trait for successful instructional leadership. Administrators who excelled in communication were better equipped to articulate expectations and promote collaboration among faculty members. Interview participants emphasized that clear communication helped convey goals and fostered a sense of unity among staff, leading to a more collaborative school culture. Furthermore, making sound decisions, particularly during crises, became critical to effective leadership. Administrators who demonstrated decisiveness and clarity in their decision-making processes were more likely to gain the trust of their staff, which further enhanced their leadership effectiveness.

Administrators who exhibited adaptability were perceived as more effective in addressing challenges such as curriculum changes or unforeseen crises. Interviewees noted that flexibility in leadership allowed for timely interventions and adjustments, which directly contributed to improved overall school performance. One administrator mentioned, "Being adaptable means we can respond quickly to challenges, whether a sudden shift in curriculum or unexpected events that disrupt our plans." This adaptability enabled administrators to implement necessary changes swiftly, ensuring that instructional practices aligned with the evolving needs of students and the school community.

Overall, the results underscore the significant impact of emotional intelligence, communication skills, decision-making abilities, and adaptability on the effectiveness of instructional leadership. These traits contribute to individual leadership success and foster a more supportive and collaborative school environment, ultimately enhancing student outcomes.

CONCLUSION

This study underscores the significance of particular administrator traits in determining the effectiveness of instructional leadership. The findings reveal that emotional intelligence, adaptability, communication skills, and decision-making abilities are crucial factors influencing the capacity of school administrators to lead effectively in instructional settings.

Emotional Intelligence: The study highlighted that administrators with high emotional intelligence are better equipped to build and maintain positive relationships with teachers. This ability to empathize and understand the emotional needs of staff fosters a supportive environment conducive to instructional improvement. Given educators' challenges, administrators who can navigate emotional dynamics are more likely to motivate their teams and enhance overall morale.

Adaptability: The capacity for adaptability emerged as essential in navigating the ever-changing education landscape. Administrators who demonstrate flexibility can respond effectively to new challenges involving curriculum changes or unexpected events. This adaptability allows for timely interventions but also helps to maintain stability and continuity in the school environment, which is crucial for sustaining instructional quality.

Communication Skills: Effective communication was identified as a foundational trait for successful instructional leadership. Administrators who can articulate clear expectations and foster open dialogue among staff create a collaborative culture that enhances teaching and learning. Communicating effectively also promotes trust and transparency within the school community, which is vital for achieving common goals.

Decision-Making: The ability to make sound and timely decisions, particularly during crises, significantly impacts instructional leadership effectiveness. Administrators with solid decision-making skills can navigate complex situations and instill confidence among their staff. This decisiveness is essential for maintaining a positive school climate and meeting instructional goals.

The insights gained from this study provide a valuable framework for enhancing leadership-training programs. By developing these critical traits, educational institutions can better prepare administrators to lead effectively. Moreover, these findings can inform future policy decisions regarding school administrators' selection and professional development, emphasizing the need for training that prioritizes emotional intelligence, adaptability, communication, and decision-making skills.

Furthermore, developing these traits among school administrators is crucial for enhancing individual leadership effectiveness and boosting overall school performance and student outcomes. As educational challenges evolve, it becomes increasingly important to equip school leaders with the skills necessary to foster a culture of academic excellence and address the diverse needs of both students and educators.

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